

TEACHING EFFECTIVENESS OF COLLEGE MICROBIOLOGY AND PARASITOLOGY CONSTRUCTIVIST-BASED MODULE IN A LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PLATFORM

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ABSTRACT

Learner's acquisition of knowledge is constantly evolving and currently inclined to technology. Thus, this study was conducted to determine the effectiveness of a Constructivist-based Module in College Microbiology and Parasitology utilizing learning management system platform. The researcher employed quasi-experimental research, specifically the non-equivalent group pretest and posttest design. The study accounted for the college science students with Microbiology and Parasitology subject at the Institute of Education. Further, the study utilized a teacher-made parallel test and the developed constructivist-based module to gather data. The mean percentage score was used to describe the performance of students' mastery levels. Moreover, the quality of data was assured through the employment of KR20 in the treatment of pretest and posttest results. Subsequently, the study also used the t-test that determined whether the significant difference between the control and experimental groups' pretest and posttest scores was evident. The study's findings revealed an increase in the performance level of students in the control group that utilized the printed constructivist-based module and in the experimental group that used the constructivist-based module introduced in a learning management system platform concerning cognitive skills. Further results indicated no significant difference in the control and experimental groups' posttest scores in cognitive skills. The study's findings suggest that students can engage their learning efficiently by utilizing the constructivist-based module in college Microbiology and Parasitology both in printed and in learning management system platform. Further recommendations for future researches that entails other biological subjects, and pure experimental research design be conducted.

Keywords: *constructivist-based module; microbiology and parasitology; learning management system platform*

INTRODUCTION

The consideration of technological advancements through online learning is seen as among the demanding components of education nowadays; the 21st-century schooling conditions require that educators be dynamic in connecting teaching and learning undertakings to the digital network age. Thus, educators of the present day must possess the traits of being positive in utilizing an explorative approach, user design, and actively constructing knowledge rather than receiving it passively, promoting learning, and constructively and appropriately incorporating technology to enhance learning. Included in the direction of Higher Education Programs need educators to be equipped in their professional expertise to employ updated content understanding and teaching methodology. Included in the objectives for professional upliftment is teaching transformation, like implementing up-to-date approaches in the learning process, utilizing 21st-century skills, and promoting the ideas of constructivism (Buenvinida et al., 2020).

Additionally, learning through the constructivist module effectively improves concept reconstruction and students' learning outcomes (Ramadhani et al., 2020). Duyilemi and Bolajoko (2014), also inspected the effects of the constructivist learning method on students' achievement and retention in Biology, and they found the pretest and posttest scores of the learners were with significant difference. As also described by Sudarwati (2013) and Salve and Opina (2014) in their study, the online module is intended to be designed to bridge any issues of difficulty in learning and help augment learning outcomes.

The mentioned claims are strengthened by Cannarelli (2016) in his study that the utilization of technology is becoming substantial and can be of great significance to the academic arena. Thus, online learning can be a means of the future. His study also described the review on the premise of backing up constructivism and its connection to an online learning module. The learners can count on constructivism to grasp a new set of knowledge based on their own experiences, and this can be achieved through the adoption of learning modules. This will occur when a teacher uses the potentialities of the learning conditions since technology is always in its advancing state. The researcher considered the utilization of constructivism as connected to an online learning module through the use of a learning management system.

Thus, the advent of a worldwide trend in creating a novel design for acquiring knowledge for the 21st-century era has asserted that classroom-based learning should be modified into a type that can give students a chance to overcome worldwide issues. However, the consideration of instruction for the twenty-first century is as critical as recognizing the present efficacy in ways of learning that are significant for the students to flourish in their studies (Scott, 2015).

Parasitology with Laboratory are biological fields that are known to be challenging major subjects for college students under the Bachelor of Secondary Education primary in Sciences. Biological subjects that include Microbiology and Parasitology have been identified with arising difficulties in the teaching facet. Thus, educators have to traverse and possibly take positive actions in engaging in an innovative endeavor to achieve a quality learning process. Based on the cited circumstances, the researcher is urged to assess the effectiveness of a Constructivist-based Module in college Microbiology and Parasitology using the learning management system to allow the learners to discover, organize their understanding, and appropriately promote interaction between themselves and the environment.

Research Questions

The primary purpose of the research was to determine the effectiveness of a Constructivist-based Module in College Microbiology and Parasitology. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What is the performance level of the college students in Microbiology and Parasitology in terms of the cognitive skills in the control and experimental group before and after the use of the Constructivist-based Module in terms of:
 - 1.1 Knowledge;
 - 1.2 Comprehension;
 - 1.3 Application; and
 - 1.4 Analysis?
2. Is there a significant difference in the pretest and posttest scores of the control group in terms of cognitive skills?
3. Is there a significant difference in the pretest and posttest scores of the experimental group in terms of cognitive skills?
4. Is there a significant difference in the posttest scores of the control and experimental group in terms of cognitive skills?

METHODOLOGY

The study made use of quasi-experimental research, specifically the non-equivalent group pretest and posttest design. Thomas (2020) stressed that a quasi-experimental method could cater to the establishment of the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The dependent variable, which includes cognitive skills, was measured once before the treatment was implemented through the pretest design and after it was implemented through the post-test design. This was conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of a constructivist-based online module in a class setting. The experimental group was taught with the developed and evaluated constructivist module in College Microbiology and Parasitology using the Learning Management System (LMS) platform. At the same time, the control group was given a printed copy of the constructivist module in College Microbiology and Parasitology. The study accounted for the college students enrolled in Microbiology and Parasitology subjects under the Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Sciences of the Institute of Education. The analysis was employed in one section only, where all the respondents were involved in the quasi-experimental research since the study was conducted during the height of the pandemic, and the researcher was restricted to conducting the study in other higher learning institutions. An experimental group composed of 17 respondents received the treatment, while the control group that did not receive the treatment was formed of 17 respondents. The study utilized a teacher-made test, a constructivist-based module, and the descriptive equivalent for the taxonomy of domains. The researcher used a parallel validated teacher-made test as one of the research instruments that is composed of the learning competencies as prescribed in the content standard of Microbiology and Parasitology subject, patterned from CHED's Policy, Standard, and Guidelines. Activities that commenced during the instrument development included the preparation of the test, preliminary field testing, revision, and final field testing. The use of a constructivist-based online module was also very significant for the accomplishment of the study. The instructional material was developed with learning qualities, namely interactive, collaborative, integrative, and inquiry-based.

The researchers also used the four-step constructivist model, which was adapted from the Learning Generative Model of Cosgrove and Osborne (1985) that constituted the students' activities, such as: Eliciting student's pre-existing ideas; Focusing on the target concept; Challenging students' ideas; and Applying newly constructed ideas to a similar situation. The constructivist-based online module underwent validation using the guidelines set by the Davao del Norte State College Guidelines and Procedures for Selecting, Evaluating, and Adopting Instructional Materials. The mean percentage score was used to describe the performance of students' mastery levels. Moreover, the quality of the data was assured using pretest, and posttest through the employment of KR20. This enabled the researcher to craft tests that took account of both validity and reliability. Aside from the first two statistical tools, the study also used the t-test to determine whether the control and experimental pretest and posttest scores were significant or not.

RESULTS

The data gathered were presented, analyzed, interpreted, and presented through the use of tables.

Table 1. Performance Level of the Control Group in terms of Cognitive Skills

Content Areas	Pretest		Posttest	
	MPS	Descriptive Equivalent	MPS	Descriptive Equivalent
Knowledge	85.00	Good	98.06	Excellent
Comprehension	69.50	Failed	93.13	Very Good
Application	75.19	Passed	95.31	Excellent
Analysis	76.50	Satisfactory	88.13	Good
Overall	76.55	Satisfactory	93.66	Very Good

Table 2. Performance Level of the Experimental Group in terms of Cognitive Skills

Content Areas	Pretest		Posttest	
	MPS	Descriptive Equivalent	MPS	Descriptive Equivalent
Knowledge	76.25	Passed	97.50	Excellent
Comprehension	66.06	Failed	90.81	Very Good
Application	68.94	Failed	100.00	Excellent
Analysis	68.69	Failed	88.19	Good
Overall	69.99	Failed	94.13	Very Good

Table 3. Summary Table for t-Test in the Pretest and Posttest of the Control Group for Cognitive Skills

Content Areas	Test	Mean Score	SD	t-value	p-value	Decision @ $\alpha = 0.05$
Knowledge	Pretest	85.00	7.30	-6.79	0.000*	Significant
	Posttest	98.06	3.91			

Comprehension	Pretest	69.50	8.52	-8.57	0.000*	Significant
	Posttest	93.13	7.80			
Application	Pretest	75.19	10.29	-5.10	0.000*	Significant
	Posttest	95.31	10.08			
Analysis	Pretest	76.50	11.17	-3.48	0.003*	Significant
	Posttest	88.13	8.11			

Table 4. Summary Table for t-Test in the Pretest and Posttest of the Experimental Group for Cognitive Skills

Content Areas	Test	Mean Score	SD	t-value	p-value	Decision @ $\alpha = 0.05$
Knowledge	Pretest	76.25	9.75	-7.76	0.000*	Significant
	Posttest	97.50	3.22			
Comprehension	Pretest	66.06	7.94	-9.06	0.000*	Significant
	Posttest	90.81	6.85			
Application	Pretest	68.94	10.17	-12.22	0.000*	Significant
	Posttest	100.00	0.00			
Analysis	Pretest	68.69	10.67	-6.65	0.000*	Significant
	Posttest	88.19	6.11			

Table 5. Summary Table for t-Test in the Posttest of the Control and Experimental Group for Cognitive Skills

Variables	Control Group	Experimental Group	t-value	p-value	Decision @ $\alpha = 0.05$
Knowledge	98.06	97.50	-0.13	0.898	Not Significant
Comprehension	93.13	90.81			
Application	95.31	100.00			
Analysis	88.13	88.19			

DISCUSSION

Based on the presented results, table 1 depicts the overall pretest results on the performance level of the control group with a mean grade of 76.55 described as Satisfactory, while their level of performance significantly increased after the administration of the posttest, as evidenced by a mean grade of 93.66 described as Very Good. As Ramadhani, et al. (2020) in their study concluded, that learning through the constructivist module effectively improves concept reconstruction and students' learning outcomes. Moreover, table 2 reveals a failed pretest descriptive equivalent of the mean percentage scores of the experimental group in terms of cognitive skills. However, there was a significant increase in the level of performance of the experimental group in their posttest that marked as 94.13 and described as Very Good. The

results further imply that the utilization of the constructivist online learning module significantly supports the experimental group improved their level of performance. This is further supported by Salve and Opina (2014), as they explained that when functional online modules are utilized in the educational system, students will find them highly fulfilling.

Moreover, table 3 exhibits all content areas under the cognitive skills of the control group and were found to have significant differences based on their pretest and posttest results. This denotes that the embedded level of cognitive skill tests that includes knowledge, comprehension, application, and analysis in the constructivist-based module impacted the improved performance of students in the control group. Further, table 4 shows the results of pretest and posttest scores of students under the experimental group, where all the content areas of cognitive skills as investigated were with significant differences. This signifies that the utilization of a constructivist-based module in a learning management system platform by the experimental group supports their performance in College Microbiology and Parasitology. As cited in the study of Cannarelli (2016), the utilization of technology is becoming substantial and can be of great significance to the academic arena. Thus, online learning can be a means of the future. His study also described the review on the premise of backing up constructivism and its connection to an online learning module.

Moreover, the exhibited results of the posttest of the control and experimental group for cognitive skills in Table 5 with all the content areas investigated were with no significant differences. This denotes that the utilization of the constructivist-based module in a learning management system platform embedded with cognitive skills improved the performance of students in College Microbiology and Parasitology subject. The results can be tailored to the study of Duyilemi and Bolajoko (2014), when they inspected the effects of constructivist learning method on students' achievement and retention in Biology. They found out a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the students.

Conclusions

The performance level of students of the control and experimental groups in terms of the cognitive skills exceeded the achievement standard and demonstrated progress toward mastery of the knowledge and skills needed in the content area tested. In addition, the control group's pretest and posttest scores using the constructivist-based printed module in terms of cognitive skills showed a significant difference. Therefore, it can be concluded that the utilization of the instructional material enhanced the performance level of college students. Further, a significant difference in the experimental group's pretest and posttest scores using the module in a learning management system in terms of cognitive skills was observed, thus it can be established that the use of the instructional material effectively improves the performance level of students. However, there was no significant difference in the pretest and posttest scores of the control and experimental groups in terms of content mastery and cognitive skills, which can be concluded that both the printed constructivist-based module and the one that was introduced in the learning management system were of equal efficacy in the learner's knowledge acquisition.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the gathered data and the conclusions, the researchers suggest the utilization of a constructivist-based module in college Microbiology and Parasitology in both printed and in the learning management system platform of teaching since it significantly improves the performance level of the control and experimental groups. Moreover, the use of constructivist-based modules in a learning management system is highly recommended to cater to the 21st-century learner's skills. The researchers also suggest that further study may be conducted on other biological subjects to assess students' performance in learning using the constructivist-based module. In addition, the researchers further stress that the same study using pure experimental design may be conducted in the future.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers observed the confidentiality of the gathered data, and was remained private. The study underwent a plagiarism check. The researchers also observed no bias in the interpretation of the findings, and the results were used purely for research done by the researchers.

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REFERENCES

- Buenvinida, L. P., Rodriguez, M. T. M., & Sapin, S. B. (2020). 21ST Century Characteristics of Educators as Perceived by Laguna State Polytechnic University Faculty. *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal*, 7(4) 398-410
- Cannarelli, G. (2016). *E-Learning: How Constructivist Learning Theory Guides Module Learning*. School of Arts and Science State University of New York Polytechnic Institute Utica, NY.
- Duyilemi, A.N. & Bolajoko, A.A. (2014). Effects of constructivists' learning strategies on senior secondary school students' achievement and retention in biology. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(27), 81-88.
- Ramadhani, R., Abdullah, A., Hasanuddin, H., Khairil, K. & Muhibbuddin (2020). The implementation of constructivist modules to correct misconceptions on the human reproductive system concept. *Journal of Physics : Conf. Ser.* 1460 012062
- Salve, A. & Opina (2014). The Development and Validation of Online Learning Modules for College English. *American International Journal of Contemporary Research*, 4(2), 89- 97.
- Scott, C. (2015). *The futures of learning 2: What kind of learning for the 21st century? (ERF Working Paper No. 14)*. Paris: UNESCO Education Research and Foresight. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000242996>
- Sudarwati, N. 2013. Developing an Integrated Module on Entrepreneurship to Improve Ability in Making Business Plans. *International Journal of Business, Humanities and Technology*, 3 (5), 109-135.

Thomas, L. (2020). *An introduction to quasi-experimental designs*.
<https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/quasi-experimental-design/>